

GENERALIZED U-H STABILITY OF CUBIC MAPPINGS

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ABSTRACT. In this work, we investigate the generalized Ulam-Hyers stability of the ω -dimensional cubic functional equation

$$\begin{aligned} \wp\left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \kappa \varkappa_i\right) &= \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda} + \eta \varkappa_{\eta}) + (3-n) \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda}) \\ &+ \left(\frac{\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6}{2}\right) \sum_{\kappa=0}^{\omega-1} (\kappa + 1)^3 \wp(\varkappa_{\kappa} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

where $\omega \geq 4$, in Banach spaces using direct and fixed point methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

The stability problem for functional equations starts from the famous talk of Ulam and the partial solutions of Hyers [9] to the Ulams problem (see [16, 17]). Since then a great deal of work has been done by a number of authors and the problems concerned with the generalizations and the applications of the stability to a number of functional equations have been developed as well [1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. Jun and Kim [12] introduced the following cubic functional equation

$$\wp(2\varkappa + \mu) + \wp(2\varkappa - \mu) = 2\wp(\varkappa + \mu) + 2\wp(\varkappa - \mu) + 12\wp(\varkappa) \quad (1.1)$$

and they established the general solution and the generalized Hyers-Ulam stability for the functional equation 1.1. The function satisfies the functional equation 1.1, which is thus called a cubic functional equation. Every solution of the cubic functional equation is said to be cubic function. One of the most important problems in fuzzy topology is too obtain an appropriate concept. The applications of the stability to a number of functional equations have been developed as well. Recently, Choonkil Park and Dong Yun Shin [3] prove the Hyers-Ulam stability of Cauchy additive functional inequality, the Cauchy additive functional equation and quadratic functional equation in matrix paranormed spaces. Furthermore, some of the other few functional equations paper are very useful to develop this paper such as [10, 11, 13, 14, 15, 18].

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In this work, we investigate the generalized Ulam-Hyers stability of the ω -dimensional cubic functional equation

$$\begin{aligned} \wp\left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \kappa \varkappa_i\right) &= \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda} + \eta \varkappa_{\eta}) + (3 - n) \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda}) \\ &+ \left(\frac{\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6}{2}\right) \sum_{\kappa=0}^{\omega-1} (\kappa + 1)^3 \wp(\varkappa_{\kappa} + 1) \end{aligned} \tag{1.2}$$

where $\omega \geq 4$, in Banach spaces using direct and fixed point methods.

Theorem 1.1. Banach Contraction Principle: Let $(\chi; d)$ be a complete metric space and consider a mapping $\Phi : \chi \rightarrow \chi$ which is strictly contractive mapping, that is

- (B1) $d(\Phi \varkappa; \Phi \mu) \leq Ld(\varkappa, \mu)$ for some (Lipschitz constant) $L < 1$, then
 - (1) The mapping Φ has one and only fixed point $\varkappa^* = \Phi(\varkappa^*)$;
 - (2) The fixed point for each given element \varkappa^* is globally attractive that is
- (B2) $\lim_{\omega \rightarrow \infty} \Phi^{\omega} \varkappa = \omega^*$, for any starting point $\varkappa \in \chi$;
 - (1) One has the following estimation inequalities:
- (B3) $d(\Phi^{\omega} \varkappa, \varkappa^*) \leq \frac{1}{1-L} d(\Phi^{\omega} \varkappa, \Phi^{\omega+1} \varkappa)$ for all $\omega \geq 0, \varkappa \in \chi$.
- (B4) $d(\varkappa, \varkappa^*) \leq \frac{1}{1-L} d(\varkappa, \varkappa^*) \forall \varkappa \in \chi$.

We take χ be a normed space and Υ be a Banach space. For notational handiness, we define a function $F : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \wp(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_n) &= \wp\left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \kappa \varkappa_{\kappa}\right) - \sum_{\kappa=1, \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda} + \eta \varkappa_{\eta}) \\ &- (3 - n) \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda}) \\ &+ \left(\frac{\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6}{2}\right) \sum_{\kappa=0}^{\omega-1} (\kappa + 1)^3 \wp(\varkappa_{\kappa} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

2. U - H STABILITY OF AN CUBIC FUNCTIONAL EQUATION 1.2 USING DIRECT METHOD

In this section, the authors discussed the generalized Ulam-Hyers stability of ω -dimensional functional equation 1.2 in Banach space using Direct Method.

Theorem 2.1. Let $\gamma \in \{-1, 1\}$. Let $\varphi : \chi^{\omega} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function such that $\sum_{\xi=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varphi(2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_1, 2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_2, \dots, 2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_n)}{2^{3\xi\gamma}}$ converges in \mathbb{R} and

$$\lim_{\xi \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\varphi(2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_1, 2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_2, \dots, 2^{\xi\gamma} \varkappa_{\omega})}{2^{3\xi\gamma}} = 0 \tag{2.1}$$

for all $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega} \in \chi$. If a function $\wp : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ be a function satisfies

$$\|\Delta \wp(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_n)\| \leq \varphi(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_n) \tag{2.2}$$

for all $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega} \in \chi$, then there exist a unique cubic function $C : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ which satisfies the functional equation 1.2 and

$$\|\wp(\varkappa) - C(\varkappa)\| \leq \frac{1}{8(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)} \sum_{\xi=\frac{1-\gamma}{2}}^{\infty} \frac{\psi(2^{\xi\gamma})}{2^{3\xi\gamma}} \tag{2.3}$$

where

$$\psi(\varkappa) = \varphi(\varkappa, \varkappa, 0, \dots, 0) \quad (2.4)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$: The function C is given by

$$C(\varkappa) = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\wp(2^{\xi\gamma})\varkappa}{2^{3\xi\gamma}} \quad (2.5)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$.

Proof. Assume that $\gamma = 1$. Replacing $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_\omega$ by $(\varkappa, \varkappa, 0, \dots, 0)$ in 1.2, we get

$$\|8(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)\wp(\varkappa) - (\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)\wp(2\varkappa)\| \leq \varphi(\varkappa, \varkappa, 0, \dots, 0) \quad (2.6)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. It follows from 2.6 that

$$\left\| \frac{\wp(2\varkappa)}{2^3} - \wp(\varkappa) \right\| \leq \frac{1}{8(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)} \varphi(\varkappa, \varkappa, 0, \dots, 0) \quad (2.7)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Now replacing \varkappa by $2\varkappa$ and dividing by 2^3 in 2.7, we arrive

$$\left\| \frac{\wp(2^2\varkappa)}{2^6} - \frac{\wp(2\varkappa)}{2^3} \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2^6(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)} \varphi(2\varkappa, 2\varkappa, 0, \dots, 0) \quad (2.8)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Adding 2.7 and 2.8, we have

$$\left\| \frac{\wp(2^2\varkappa)}{2^3} - \wp(\varkappa) \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2^3(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)} \left(\varphi(\varkappa, \varkappa, 0, \dots, 0) + \frac{\varphi(2\varkappa, 2\varkappa, 0, \dots, 0)}{2^3} \right)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. In general for any positive integer δ , one can easy to verify that

$$\left\| \frac{\wp(2^\delta\varkappa)}{2^{3\delta}} - \wp(\varkappa) \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2^3} \sum_{\xi=0}^{\infty} \frac{\psi(2^\xi\varkappa)}{2^{3\xi\gamma}} \quad (2.9)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. In order to prove the convergence of the sequence $\{\frac{\wp(2^\delta\varkappa)}{2^{3\delta}}\}$, replacing \varkappa by $2^\tau\varkappa$ and dividing $2^{3\tau}$ in 2.9, for $\delta, \nu > 0$, we get

$$\left\| \frac{\wp(2^{\delta+\tau}\varkappa)}{2^{3\delta+3\tau}} - \frac{\wp(2^\tau\varkappa)}{2^{3\tau}} \right\| \leq \frac{1}{2^3} \sum_{\xi=0}^{\delta-1} \frac{\psi(2^{\xi+\tau}\varkappa)}{2^{3(\xi+\tau)}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \tau \rightarrow \infty \quad (2.10)$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Hence the sequence $\{\frac{\wp(2^\delta\varkappa)}{2^{3\delta}}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence. Since Υ is complete, there exists a mapping $C : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ such that

$$C(\varkappa) = \lim_{\delta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\wp(2^\delta\varkappa)}{2^{3\delta}}$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Letting $\delta \rightarrow \infty$ in 2.9 we see that 2.4 holds for $\varkappa \in \chi$. To prove that C satisfies 1.2, replacing $(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_\omega)$ by $(2^\tau\varkappa, 2^\tau\varkappa, \dots, 2^\tau\varkappa)$ and dividing $2^{3\tau}$ in 2.2, we arrive

$$\frac{1}{2^{3\tau}} \|\Delta\wp((2^\tau\varkappa, 2^\tau\varkappa, \dots, 2^\tau\varkappa))\| \leq \frac{1}{2^{3\tau}} \varphi((2^\tau\varkappa, 2^\tau\varkappa, \dots, 2^\tau\varkappa))$$

for all $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_\omega \in \chi$. Letting $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ in above inequality and using the definition of $C(\varkappa)$, we see that $C(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_\omega) = 0$. Hence C satisfies 1.2 for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. To show

that C is unique. Let Δ be the another cubic mapping satisfying 1.2 and 2.4, then

$$\begin{aligned} \|C(\varkappa) - \Delta(\varkappa)\| &\leq \frac{1}{2^{3\tau}} \{ \|C(2^\tau \varkappa) - \wp(2^\tau)\| + \|\Delta(2^\tau \varkappa)\| \} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2^3} \sum_{\xi=0}^{\infty} \frac{\psi(2^{\xi+\tau} \varkappa)}{2^{3(\xi+\tau)}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \tau \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Hence C is unique. For $\gamma = -1$, we can prove a similar stability result. The proof is completed. \square

The following corollary is an immediate consequence of Theorem 1.1, concerning the stability of 1.2.

Corollary 2.2. *Let ϕ and δ be a positive real numbers. Let $\wp : \varkappa \in \chi$ be a function satisfying the inequality*

$$\|\Delta_{\wp}(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega})\| \leq \begin{cases} \phi \\ \phi \left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\delta} \right) \\ \phi \left(\prod_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\delta} \right) + \left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\omega\delta} \right) \end{cases}$$

for all $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega} \in \chi$. Then there exists a unique cubic function $C : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ such that

$$\|\wp(\varkappa) - C(\varkappa)\| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{\phi}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)|7|} \\ \frac{2\phi\|\varkappa\|}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)2^3 - 2^{\delta}}; & \delta \neq 3 \\ \frac{2\phi\|\varkappa\|}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)2^3 - 2^{\omega\delta}}; & \delta \neq \frac{3}{\omega} \end{cases}$$

3. U - H STABILITY OF AN CUBIC FUNCTIONAL EQUATION 1.2 USING FIXED POINT METHOD

In this section, we found the generalized Ulam-Hyers stability of the ω -dimensional functional equation (1.2) in Banach space with the help of fixed point method.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $\wp : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ be a mapping for which there exists a function $\Phi : \chi^{\omega} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ with the condition*

$$\lim_{\xi \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\Phi(\rho_{\kappa}^{\varkappa_1}, \rho_{\kappa}^{\varkappa_2}, \dots, \rho_{\kappa}^{\varkappa_{\omega}})}{\rho_{\kappa}^{3\xi}} = 0 \tag{3.1}$$

where

$$\rho_{\kappa} = \begin{cases} 2, & \text{if } \kappa = 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } \kappa = 1 \end{cases}$$

such that the functional inequality

$$\|\Delta_{\wp}(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega})\| \leq \Phi(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega}) \tag{3.2}$$

for all $\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega} \in \chi$. If there exist $L = L(\kappa)$ such that the function

$$\varkappa \rightarrow \psi(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6} \Phi\left(\frac{\varkappa}{2}, \frac{\varkappa}{2}, 0, \dots, 0\right)$$

has the property

$$\frac{1}{\rho_{\kappa}^4} \nu(\rho_{\kappa} \varkappa) = L\nu(\varkappa) \tag{3.3}$$

for all $\varkappa \in \chi$. Then there exists a unique cubic function $C : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ satisfying the functional equation 1.2 and

$$\|\wp(\varkappa) - C(\varkappa)\| \leq \frac{L^{1-\kappa}}{1-L} \nu(\varkappa) \quad (3.4)$$

holds for all $\varkappa \in \chi$.

Corollary 3.2. Let ϕ and δ be a non-negative real numbers. Let $\wp : \varkappa \in \chi$ be a function satisfying the inequality

$$\|\Delta_{\wp}(\varkappa_1, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega})\| \leq \begin{cases} \phi \\ \phi \left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\delta} \right) \\ \phi \left(\prod_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\delta} \right) + \left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \|\varkappa_{\kappa}\|^{\omega\delta} \right) \end{cases}$$

for all $\text{arkappa}_{\omega_1}, \varkappa_2, \dots, \varkappa_{\omega} \in \chi$. Then there exists a unique cubic function $C : \chi \rightarrow \Upsilon$ such that

$$\|\wp(\varkappa) - C(\varkappa)\| \leq \begin{cases} \frac{\phi}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)|7|} \\ \frac{2\phi\|\varkappa\|}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)2^3 - 2^{\delta}}; & \delta \neq 3 \\ \frac{2\phi\|\varkappa\|}{(\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6)2^3 - 2^{\omega\delta}}; & \delta \neq \frac{3}{\omega} \end{cases}$$

4. CONCLUSION

We have introduced the following functional equation

$$\begin{aligned} \wp\left(\sum_{\kappa=1}^{\omega} \kappa \varkappa_i\right) &= \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda} + \eta \varkappa_{\eta}) + (3-n) \sum_{\kappa=1; \kappa \neq \lambda \neq \eta}^{\omega} \wp(\kappa \varkappa_{\kappa} + \lambda \varkappa_{\lambda}) \\ &+ \left(\frac{\omega^2 - 5\omega + 6}{2}\right) \sum_{\kappa=0}^{\omega-1} (\kappa+1)^3 \wp(\varkappa_{\kappa} + 1). \end{aligned}$$

We have solved the n -dimensional non-quadratic functional equation and also investigated the Hyers-Ulam stability of the new type of the functional equation using direct and fixed point methods.

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